

Unbreakable MEAN GIRLS:
A Study of Tina Fey's Portrayal of (Self) Sexualized Teens
Mo Ibrahim

Before Tina Fey created *Unbreakable Kimmy Schmidt* and *Mr. Mayor* and wrote the *Mean Girls* oeuvre, she was a cast member and writer for *Saturday Night Live*. A study of *Unbreakable Kimmy Schmidt*, *Mean Girls*, and *Mr. Mayor* revealed that Fey's works included a number of portrayals of self-sexualized teens. In other words, Fey's teens freely and openly engaged in alluring sexual activity. For example, 16-year-old Karen of *Mean Girls* had consensual sex with *eleven* different partners. When Karen was 13, she sexted nudes to a boy, which were posted on Amateurtweens.com. And Karen wore skirts that barely covered her "perky" heinie. What follows is a study of Fey's portrayal of self-sexualized teens.

In 2021, a Gen Z-er, with whom I share a common sense of humor, suggested that I watch Netflix's *Unbreakable Kimmy Schmidt* (2015). Here's James Hake's *IMDB* storyline of the comedy series:

After being rescued from an underground bunker in which she lived the past fifteen years, Kimmy Schmidt decides to move to New York City to have a normal life. She makes friends with her new roommate Titus, and works as a babysitter for Jacqueline Voorhees, the wife of a billionaire with many issues. Even though many obstacles are thrown her way, Kimmy makes the best of her new life while adapting to the new world around her.

On the second episode of the premiere season, "Kimmy Gets a Job!" (2015), which was co-written by Fey, 15-year-old Xanthippe Voorhees and Simone, Xanthippe's bestie, were playing "vodka shotzee" when Simone, a *modelesque* (honey) blond, got alcohol poisoning.

Xanthippe warned that they couldn't have Simone's stomach pumped at the hospital, because Simone's dad was running for Congress. Consequently, Kimmy made a vomit-inducing concoction, but she advised Simone to see a doctor to which Xanthippe replied, "Her boyfriend's an ophthalmologist, but he's on vacation with his wife." That's correct. Simone, who streamers could confidently infer was 15 too, had a boyfriend who was a married ophthalmologist!

Later in the episode, Simone shared, "You guys, I was showering [post sex] with Dr. Jerry, and he told me he hates his wife," to which Xanthippe exclaimed, "You're so lucky!"

Not to be outdone, Xanthippe shared, to Kimmy's utter surprise, that she had sex with a blond surfer on a California beach while visiting her grandparents to which Simone related, "I have sex when I visit my grandparents too." However, Xanthippe and Simone did not clarify if they were having age-gap (outdoor) sex while visiting their grandparents.

On "Kimmy's in a Love Triangle!" (season 01 episode 10), which was co-written by Fey, Xanthippe was informed that, due to an impending divorce, she had to move back to Connecticut with her birth mother since Jacqueline was her step-mother. Consequently, Xanthippe pleaded with Kimmy to help her find a way to remain in New York City. Xanthippe said that her entire life would be taken away by moving to Connecticut. For example, she would lose her school and friends. And she would lose her dad's friend whom gave her jewelry in exchange for her old retainers. Xanthippe implored, "Imagine you're 15. One day your whole life gets taken from you. Your school. Your friends. Your dad's friend who buys you jewelry when you send him your old retainers."

About a year after I streamed *Unbreakable Kimmy Schmidt*, I read Jake Viswanath's post on *Bustle*: "Amanda Seyfried Reflects On *Mean Girls* [2004] & 'Gross' Remarks That Men Made After It" (May 11, 2022) For some context, in the film, that was co-written by Fey, 16-year-old Karen Smith (Amanda Seyfried) could tell when it was going to rain due to a feeling in her fountains. While squeezing her teen breasts, Karen shared with Cady, "My breasts can always tell when it's gonna rain." Consequently, Karen was given the role of North Shore High School's weatherwoman, and she reported, "Hi. This is Karen Smith. It's 68 degrees." And as she massaged her right and then left breast, she reported, "And there's a 30 percent chance that it's already raining."

Viswanath wrote that Seyfried said that some male fans took the joke that Fey wrote "too far in real life" and that some fans "crossed a line into catcalling". (Note that Seyfried implied that if she were *not* a nymphet, the catcalling would not have been gross.) Viswanath wrote:

Karen Smith from *Mean Girls* is a bonafide meteorologist icon, but sometimes, fans took the joke too far in real life. Amanda Seyfried, who played Karen, just revealed how male fans would often ask her if it was raining after the premiere of *Mean Girls* in 2004 [...] Fans' references to the joke often crossed a line into catcalling, especially given Seyfried's age at the time. "I always felt really grossed out by that," Seyfried told *Marie Claire* in an interview published on May 11. "I was, like, 18 years old. It was just gross."

However, Seyfried had nothing but nice words to say about Mark Waters, whom directed Seyfried to massage her teen breasts, and Tina Fey, whom wrote Seyfried's lascivious lines. Seyfried said that Waters made her "look good", she said that Fey "[...] wrote the coolest script of all time.", and she referred to her performance in the film as her "best work". Viswanath wrote:

Despite the gross comments she received, Seyfried has only positive memories from filming *Mean Girls*, the movie that put her on the map, even calling it her "best work" in 2013 [...] it was written so well and so wonderfully directed. Mark Waters (the director) made me look good, he made me funny. And Tina Fey wrote the coolest script of all time. I'm so grateful for every experience."

But it wasn't until I saw the trailer on YouTube for *Mean Girls* (2018), the Broadway musical, that I began to see a pattern in Fey's writing and the portrayal of a self-sexualized teen. In the trailer for the musical, which Fey wrote the book for, Karen opened her jacket in the high school's cafeteria and jumped up and down in a suggestive manner, which drew the attention of the potential theatergoers to her bouncing teen breasts.

Thus, intrigued by Fey's work, I decided to view the Broadway musical and read Fey's libretto, which were based on the 2004 film. I streamed *Mean Girls* (2004). And I watched *Mean Girls* (2024) - a film that was, of course, co-written by Fey and based on Fey's Broadway musical. Below, before discussing Fey's *Mr. Mayor* (2021), I profiled Karen and Regina. And I covered a number of motifs of the theme of self-sexualized teens such as teens in age-gap relationships, teen *Girls Gone Wild*, and what I refer to as teen lipstick lesbianism (i.e., seemingly heterosexual teens participating in girl-on-girl sexual situations).

Karen

Here's the synopsis for *Mean Girls* (2004) from *Rotten Tomatoes*:

Teenage Cady Heron (Lindsay Lohan) was educated in Africa by her scientist parents. When her family moves to the suburbs of Illinois, Cady finally gets to experience public school and gets a quick primer on the cruel, tacit laws of popularity that divide her fellow students into tightly knit cliques. She unwittingly finds herself in the good graces of an elite group of cool

students dubbed "the Plastics," but Cady soon realizes how her shallow group of new friends earned this nickname.

We previously related that, due to a tingle in her breasts, 16-year-old Karen (Amanda Seyfried) could forecast when it was going to rain. But before Karen shared that titillating information with Cady, Karen admitted, "I can put my whole fist in my mouth!" And she asked, "Wanna see?"

Later in the film, as a girls' locker room prank, a student cut the parts of Karen's top that covered Karen's nipples. Surprisingly, Karen kept the top on, boldly bounced out of the locker room, and commenced a raunchy fashion trend at school.

In the Libretto Vocal Book *Mean Girls: High School Version* (Revised July 2022) and on the Broadway stage, during the "Meet the Plastics" song, Karen sang that her tiny skirt barely covered her "perky" heinie. (In general, on Broadway, the Plastics wore really short skirts and/or very tight pants.)

KAREN

MY NAME IS KAREN. MY HAIR IS SHINY.
MY TEETH ARE PERFECT. MY SKIRT IS TINY.
IT BARELY COVERS MY PERKY HEINY.

During the Broadway musical, theatergoers learned why Karen drew the attention of potential theatergoers to her bouncing teen breasts in the trailer. It turned out that Karen's behavior was prompted by Jason whom said that he could "guess any girl's bra size" by having her "jump one time". Consequently, Karen exclaimed, "Do me!", she opened her jacket, and jumped more than one time.

JASON W.

Hey, New Girl, you wanna see a trick? I can guess any girl's bra size. All you gotta do is jump one time-

GRETCHEN

Ew, Jason-

KAREN

Do me!

As we mention in the introduction, theatergoers learned via Gretchen that Karen was very sexually active, because despite only being 16-years-old, Gretchen related to Cady that Karen “had sex with eleven people”.

GRETCHEN

Are you a virgin?

CADY

What?

GRETCHEN

You don't have to tell me. But just know that I'm very trustworthy. Karen's had sex with eleven people and I've never told anyone.

During "Sexy", Karen sang that being the "hot one" is a "full time gig", because it takes a lot of time and energy to satisfy people's desires; however, Karen confessed that it was *her* prerogative to be sexy. While performing “Sexy”, Karen danced licentiously on the Broadway stage in a pair of bra and panties with the panties barely covered by a sheer camisole. And at one point during "Sexy", Karen turned around, lifted her camisole, and revealed her panties to the audience.

(KAREN)

WHEN YOU ARE THE HOT ONE,
IT'S A FULL TIME GIG,
LOOKING LIKE WHAT PEOPLE WANNA SEE.

KAREN

I CAN BE WHO I WANNA BE, AND SEXY

KAREN

THIS IS MODERN FEMINISM TALKIN':
I EXPECT TO RUN THE WORLD
IN SHOES I CANNOT WALK IN.
I CAN BE WHO I WANT TO BE...
AND SEX,
SEX,
SEXY!

Interestingly, and in yet another display of Fey's lack of naiveté as it relates to sexualized teens, Karen intentionally exposed her bra, because she was "going for a look". However, Karen did not specify if the look was: "girl who's slept with eleven people".

REGINA

Karen, I can see your bra.

KAREN

It's on purpose. I'm going for a look.

REGINA

Is it "girl who's slept with eleven people"? 'Cause you're nailing it.

Note that in the high school version of the libretto, Fey, ironically, offered an alternative "suggestion" for certain lines in the musical to the high school students playing high school students. For example, instead of Regina asking, "Is it "girl who's slept with eleven people"? 'Cause you're nailing it." Fey suggested that a high school student could say, "If it's 'girl who hooked up with eleven people' you're nailing it," thereby reminding theater kids that teen oral sex is less provocative than teen sex.

In the song "Stop!", Karen sang that when she was 13, she sent "nude pics" to a boy she had "a huge crush on", but Karen forgot to crop the pics, which were posted on Amateurtweens.

KAREN

STOP.

WHEN YOU HAVE A HUGE CRUSH ON A BOY
AND HE ASKS YOU TO "SEND NUDE PICS"
AND YOU'RE LIKE, "WOW HE LIKES ME!"
AND SO YOU SEND THEM BUT DON'T CROP YOUR HEAD OFF
'CAUSE YOU'RE ONLY 13 AND DON'T KNOW ANY BETTER
AND I GUESS HIS FRIENDS SHARED 'EM
'CAUSE NOW YOU'RE ALL OVER A PORN SITE
CALLED AMATEURTWEENS.

Consequently, Karen informed theatergoers, "Now I only get naked with people in person! Also, someone should teach boys not to do that in the first place." (At the Broadway performance that I saw, a number of people in the audience started clapping and hooting after those lines.)

Rhetorical question: Did Fey base Karen on Danielle Miller and Gabrielle Bluestone's *New York* magazine piece: "What Danielle Miller learned at Horace Mann and Rikers"? (FEB. 9, 2022) In the piece, Bluestone related:

In 2004, when Miller was in eighth grade, a boy she had a crush on dared her in an AIM message to prove she wasn't a "prude." She grabbed the new Sony VAIO laptop her father had given her for Christmas and propped it on the ledge of her shower stall. She disrobed, picked up the handle of a Swiffer mop, and pressed record. She made three sexual videos in all and emailed them to the boy.

The boy forwarded the clips to Miller's best friend, who in turn sent them to two people, and soon it had reached everyone that they knew. It spread rapidly from there.

The videos hadn't circulated just among New York's private-school students and their friends [...] The videos also ended up on the file-sharing programs LimeWire and Kazaa.

Unfortunately, we may never know if Fey based Karen on Swiffer Girl.

Here's the synopsis posted on Rotten Tomatoes for *Mean Girls* (2024):

From the comedic mind of Tina Fey comes a new twist on the modern classic, MEAN GIRLS. New student Cady Heron (Angourie Rice) is welcomed into the top of the social food chain by the elite group of popular girls called "The Plastics," ruled by the conniving queen bee Regina George (Reneé Rapp) and her minions Gretchen (Bebe Wood) and Karen (Avantika). However, when Cady makes the major misstep of falling for Regina's ex-boyfriend Aaron Samuels (Christopher Briney), she finds herself prey in Regina's crosshairs. As Cady sets to take down the group's apex predator with the help of her outcast friends Janis (Auli'i Cravalho) and Damian (Jaquel Spivey), she must learn how to stay true to herself while navigating the most cutthroat jungle of all: high school.

Recall that on Broadway, after Karen exclaimed, "Do me!", she opened her jacket, and bounced up and down in a manner that drew attention to her bouncing breasts. In the 2024 film version of *Mean Girls*, Karen (Avantika) performed "Sexy" during a Halloween party where she bounced up and down in a manner that drew attention to her bouncing breasts, which were partially covered by a bra; however, unlike Broadway's Karen, who performed "Sexy" in pair of panties, Karen (Avantika) performed "Sexy" in a pair of black spandex shorts. And to give moviegoers and streamers a clear view of her shorts, Karen (Avantika) bent over and lifted her camisole to reveal a letter B, a ghost, and a pumpkin (i.e., BOO) that were displayed across her derrière.

Just like in the musical, in the 2024 film, Regina informed "Karen, I can see your bra." Karen replied, "It's on purpose. I'm going for a look." And Regina asked, "Is it 'girl who slept with 11 people'? 'Cause you're nailing it." But this raises the question: Why did Fey add this salacious motif to the musical and 2024 film, because there was no apparent indication from the 2004 film that Karen was a teen nymphomaniac. On the other hand, Karen (Amanda Seyfried) *did* inform Cady, "I can put my whole fist in my mouth!"

Lastly, as it relates to Karen, in the 2024 film, while Karen filmed a social media post, Gretchen, in the background, stopped typing on her phone to analyze her derrière that was wrapped tightly in a pair of black spandex shorts. Unhappy with the extent of her buttock's bulge, Gretchen proceeded to perform squats.

Regina

In the Broadway musical, during “Meet the Plastics”, Regina sang in the cafeteria that she did *not* have any (teen) breast implants, “AND THESE? THESE ARE REAL.” To confirm Regina’s assertion, Damian squeezed her left breast. And when Regina sang, “THIS WHOLE SCHOOL HUMPS MY LEG LIKE A CHIHUAHUA”, three boys surrounded Regina and simulated sex (i.e., dry humped) on the stage floor and Regina's legs.

As it relates to Regina’s breasts, in the libretto, the ensemble merely asked about Regina’s eating habits, her fashion sense, and her dating life.

ENSEMBLE

WHAT’S REGINA EATING? WHAT’S REGINA WEARIN’?
IS SHE DATING AARON?
REGINA! REGINA!
SHE HAS EV’RYTHING”
REGINA! REGINA! REGINA!

But during the Broadway musical, the ensemble asked about Regina’s breast size.

ENSEMBLE

WHAT’S REGINA EATING? [...]
DID HER BOOBS GET BIGGER?
REGINA! REGINA! SHE HAS EV’RYTHING

Subsequently, Broadway theatergoers learned from Rachel H. that Regina was, “[...] considered the prettiest girl in school.” And that Regina *could* be nice to her friends too. For instance, in the libretto, Regina informed Cady, “I’m gonna buy you those suede heels ‘cause you need more.” More what, you may ask? Regina opined that Cady needed more: height, style, and butt lift.

CADY

(re: shoes in window) Cady, come here. I’m gonna buy you those suede heels ‘cause you need more.

CADY

More what?

REGINA

More shoes, more height, more style, more butt lift - trust me, more is better.

But during the Broadway musical Regina said, “Cady, look at the shoes. I’m gonna buy you those suede hills to lift your butt.” (Interestingly, the shoes were from Shameless Footwear.)

Due to a prank, Regina gained weight from eating Kälteen bars, which prevented her from fitting into her skirt. Consequently, she stomped around the Broadway stage in a pair of cheeky black panties before she, like Karen in the 2024 film, turned around, fully bent over, and displayed her teen fanny to the audience. (Interestingly, Regina’s panties were over a pair of nude tights that were given a “lift” with implants.)

REGINA

This skirt won't close. Cady, these Kälteen bars suck.

CADY

No, you have to make sure you eat enough carbs to...activate them.

REGINA

(at Gretchen) Stop playing with that stupid babyish book and help me find a safety pin!

REGINA holds the skirt and stomps around in her underwear. GRETCHEN flits around looking for a pin.

Eventually, Regina stopped stomping, turned around, bent over, and exposed her cheeky panties, that barely covered her vagina, to the audience.

In all three versions of *Mean Girls*, the Plastics (i.e., Cady, Gretchen, Karen, and Regina) danced seductively during the Winter Talent Show. The 2004 performance was named Jingle Bell Rock, but the Plastics in the Broadway musical and in the 2024 film performed "Rockin' Around the

Pole". In all three performances, which were staged every school year, the Plastics were dressed as sexy teen Santa's Helpers, which included Santa's hats and red *mini* skirts. While all three performances were salacious, the Broadway performance was the most salacious, because when the "Hot Elves" sang "WE'LL ROCK THAT POLE ALL NIGHT!", for the sixth year in a row, Regina's skirt fell off. To clarify, Regina's mini skirt fell to the Broadway stage to, once again, reveal her teen cheeky black panties. And once again, she turned around, bent over, and displayed herself to the audience. Consequently, there were "posts and memes of REGINA'S exposed butt" on social media, which were displayed on the stage's LED screens (e.g., OMG! OH...MY..., I'M feeling hungry!, and trishjshaw posted: Was that Regina's talent? #Glutes). Consequently, Damian asked, "Was it funny when Regina bent over and it looked like her butt ate her underwear? Yes. One million percent." But to be fair, the skirts of the "Hot [teen] Elves" were so short that all of their underwear could be briefly yet clearly seen on Broadway.

LIL BIPPY LEE (V.O.)

WE'LL ROCK THAT POLE ALL NIGHT!

Regina's skirt falls off.

REGINA

Aagh!

SHE bends over to pick it up. Everything freezes. JANIS and DAMIAN address the audience.

LED screens fill with posts and memes of REGINA'S exposed butt.

DAMIAN

Was it funny when Regina bent over and it looked like her butt ate her underwear? Yes. One million percent.

We learned throughout Fey's *Mean Girls* oeuvre, that Regina cheated on Aaron with Shane Oman. In the 2004 film, instead of doing SAT prep, Regina cheated on Aaron with Shane in the, "[...] projection room above the auditorium." In the 2024 film, Regina cheated on Aaron with Shane, "[...] in the third floor janitorial closet on the bags of sawdust that they use for barf!" However, the Broadway musical provided some detail on exactly how Regina and Shane were hooking up. On Broadway, Gretchen informed Cady that Regina was, "[...] hooking up with Shane Oman in the North Shore Lions costume!"

GRETCHEN

Also, she totally cheats on Aaron. Every Thursday she says she has SAT Prep, but really she's hooking up with Shane Oman in the North Shore Lions costume!

CADY

She makes him wear the costume?

GRETCHEN

No, they're both in the costume. And I never told anyone because I'm such a good friend."

Apparently, in this context, "hooking up" meant teen sex, because an actor in a lion costume aggressively simulated having sex. And he was *not* alone in the costume.

In addition, Damian divulged while singing "Where Do You Belong", that the high school's band members were particularly sexually active (e.g., teen oral sex and "fingering")

DAMIAN

HERE'S THE SEX'LLY ACTIVE BAND GEEKS,
I GOT TWO WORDS FOR YOU:
"EMBOUCHURE" AND "EW."
AND IF YOU LIKE BLOWING... AND FINGERING,

BAND GEEKS

THIS IS THE GROUP FOR YOU!

Just like in the Broadway musical, in the 2024 film, Regina sang, "And these are real." Thereby, reassuring filmgoers and streamers that her teen breasts did not have any implants.

However, unlike in the musical, Regina's breast was not fondled, but after Regina opened her jacket in the high school's cafeteria to reveal her cleavage, like *Price Is Right* models, Karen and Gretchen placed their hands below Regina's breasts. Thereby, leaving no doubt about what Regina was referencing.

Logically, the setting of the Broadway musical's overture was in North Shore High School's auditorium where shortly after Damian welcomed the freshmen to high school, Janis directed the theatergoers to her painting of a vagina that she said represented female teenage power.

DAMIAN

Good morning! Welcome to high school.

JANIS

"This painting I made will represent female teenage power."

Thus, Janis asserted that "female teenage power" comes from the teen vagina. And in terms of Janis, we learned from the Broadway musical that Regina didn't invite Janis to her pool party, because Regina suspected that Janis was a (teen) lesbian.

REGINA

Janis, I can't invite you to my pool party, 'cause I think you're a lesbian.

But in the 2024 film, Damian shared that *Regina* was the (lipstick) lesbian. Damian related that while middle schoolers, "[...] Regina was worried that Kyle liked Karen more." Thus, during an after (middle) school game of spin the bottle, Regina decided to seduce Kyle by putting on a "little [girl-on-girl kissing] show" by kissing Janis. Consequently, Kyle got an erection. Damian said, "[...] Kyle was like 'boing!'"

Speaking of girl-on-girl kissing, in the 2004 film, at an after-school Halloween house party, two scantily clad school girls kissed sensuously while a male student exclaimed, "Yes! Yes!" And after it was revealed that all the school girls had been backbiting each other, Ms. Norbury (Fey), a math teacher, said, "There's been some girl-on-girl crime here."

Speaking of Halloween and scantily clad school girls, in the 2004 film, Cady narrated, “In the regular world, Halloween is when children dress up in customs and beg for candy. In *Girl World*, Halloween is the one night a year when a girl can dress like a total slut and no other girls can say anything about it.” In addition, in the 2024 film and during the Broadway musical, Gretchen went even further by stating that *not* dressing like a slut (on Halloween) was, in fact, slut shaming. Gretchen opined, "Cady, if you don't dress slutty, that is slut-shamming us." Thus, it should come as no surprise that during the Broadway musical, Regina dressed as a (teen) Playboy Bunny - complete with a cheeky bottom. And during "Someone Gets Hurt", while still dressed as a Playboy Bunny, Regina placed Aaron's hand on her left breast.

Just like in the Broadway musical, in the 2024 film, Regina informed “Karen, I can see your bra.” Karen replied, “It’s on purpose. I’m going for a look.” Consequently, Regina asked, “Is it ‘girl who slept with eleven people?’” Thereby, once again, informing streamers that Karen had sex with eleven people - presumably, all before the age of 16!

Interestingly, in the 2004 film, the teens weren’t the only characters who self-sexualized. For example, Mrs. George (Amy Poehler), opened Regina's bedroom door and discovered her daughter passionately kissing Shane Oman on the bed. Shockingly yet graciously, Mrs. George offered her teen daughter and Shane snacks and a condom. Mrs. George, "You guys need anything? Some snacks? A condom? Let me know. Oh, God love you." And in the 2004 film and during the Broadway musical, upon meeting Cady for the first time, Mrs. George inexplicably shared, "We haven't had any new meat in our little lady taco in so long." However, Mrs. George didn't clarify if the "we" included her teen daughter.

As for motifs related to self-sexualized teens, there were inferences in the 2004 film to the *Girls Gone Wild* franchise. For instance, while Regina was on the phone with Cady, Regina’s preteen sister was watching a *Spring Beach Party* advertisement on television. During the advertisement a brunette and blond spring breaker raised their cropped tops to reveal their bare breasts above their bikini bottoms. Consequently, Regina’s *preteen* sister raised her top too! During an all-girl high school brawl, where a schoolboy encouraged, "Yeah! Take your top off!", the secretary informed the principal, "They've gone wild. The girls have gone wild." And in terms of schoolboys requesting the schoolgirls take their tops off, in the libretto, after Cady introduced herself to the class, Cady’s classmates demanded that she go topless.

CADY

Hello, my name if Cady Heron

STUDENTS

No one cares!/Take your top off!

However, Fey gave high school actors the: “Option not to say that line.” And those lines had been removed from the Broadway performance that I saw.

Recall that *Unbreakable Kimmy Schmidt*'s Simone had an age-gap affair with Dr. Jerry, a married ophthalmologist, whom, while showering [post sex], confessed to 15-year-old Simone that he hated his wife. And that Xanthippe received jewelry from her dad's friend in exchange for her retainers. In addition, in the libretto, Cady revealed via "Stupid With Love" that when she was a whopping 5-years-old, she, "[...] fell in love, [with] this Peace Corps guy." That's correct - not "peace corps boy" but "guy". Cady's love was unrequited, but it took eight years before she "gave up trying"!

CADY

WHEN I WAS FIVE, I FELL IN LOVE, THIS PEACE CORPS GUY
I BARED MY SOUL BESIDE THE WATER HOLE,
WHICH MADE HIM LAUGH.

CADY

BY THIRTEEN I GAVE UP TRYING

But during the Broadway musical, she sang, “WHEN I WAS FIVE, I FELL IN LOVE. IT DIDN'T LAST.” Cady didn't mention her love interest's age; however, she did share that her love interest was Kenyan. “HE RAN FROM ME. LITERALLY RAN FROM ME. AND BEING KENYAN, HE RAN FAST.” Then Cady clarified that she was actually 10-years-old when she fell in love with a Peace Corps guy. “WHEN I WAS TEN - IN LOVE AGAIN. THIS PEACE CORP GUY. I WAITED FOR HOURS - INSIDE HIS TENT WITH FLOWERS. WHICH MADE HIM LAUGH. WHICH MADE ME CRY. BY THIRTEEN, I GAVE UP TRYING.”

Yet, in the 2024 film, Cady (Angourie Rice) sang that she was 9-years-old when she fell in love with "This Peace Corps guy" and that she waited *inside* his tent with flowers.

“When I was nine\I fell I love\This Peace Corps guy\I waited hours inside his tent with flowers\Which made him laugh\Which made me cry\By 13 I gave up trying”

Cady reminded me of the film *Blame It On Rio* (1984) where 17-year-old Jennifer (Michelle Johnson) used her youthful beauty and insatiable libido to seduce Matthew (Michael Caine) - her father's 49-year-old best friend. After sex, but still in bed, Jennifer shared with Matthew that her (puppy) love for him began when she was 10-years-old. Jenner to Matthew, "I love you [...] I used to pretend [...] that we were married [...] when I was ten."

Lastly, as it relates to Cady, due to her attraction to her classmate Aaron, Cady shared that she was filled with “CALCULUST.”

Continuing with the motif of teens in age-gap relationships, in the libretto, Coach Carr made his debut by stating that during the fall semester, he was required by the state to cover abstinence; however, in the spring semester he would cover "Condoms and Choking".

COACH CARR

Welcome to "Health and Yuman Sexshiality." This fall we're gonna be doing the state-required unit on Abstinence. And then in the spring, we do Condoms and Choking.

Fey suggested that a high school student playing Coach Carr could alternatively say, “And then in the spring, we do Self-esteem and Choking.” But in the Broadway performance that I saw, Coach Carr conveniently changed choking to nutrition. “And then in the spring, we do Self-esteem and Nutrition.”

In addition to teaching his high school students how to choke each other during protected teen sex, Coach Carr had a student(s)-teacher affair with Trang Pak *and* Sun Jin Dinh that began in the 2004 film. Initially, filmgoers and streamers were shown Coach Carr and Trang Pak making out in the high school's projection room. (Note that the projection room is where Regina *hooked up* Shane.) Later it was revealed that Sun Jin Dinh had made out with Coach Carr too! Upon hearing a student read a page from the *Burn Book*, “Trang Pak made out with Coach Carr! And so did Sun Jin Dinh.” Trang and Sun verbally and physically fought over Coach Carr - in the hallway of North Shore High. Trang, “You little slut!” Sun, “You’re the slut!”

Lastly, as it relates to teens in age-gap relationships, I believe that it's safe to infer that Coach Carr, at a minimum, attempted to have a student-teacher affair with Karen, because Karen said on Broadway that Coach Carr informed her that he had an "open marriage"

KAREN

And how when Coach Carr tells me he has an "open marriage," that his wife probably doesn't know that they do.

And lastly, in terms of Coach Carr, he shared on Broadway some exclusive information with his male students about the makeup of school girls, which is that they were deranged by whoremones.

COACH CARR

[...] here's what no one's gonna tell ya. Girls are made deranged by what's called hormones. Hormones.

(COACH CARR)

(writes on the board)

W.H.O.R. -

BELL RINGS.

Mr. Mayor

Here's the synopsis for NBC's *Mr. Mayor* from *Rotten Tomatoes*:

When retired Los Angeles businessman Neil Bremer decides to run for mayor of his beloved city, he surprises everyone and wins the seat. With great ideas and commitment to the community, he optimistically sets out to get to work shaking up City Hall. However, he quickly discovers navigating politics is not business as usual [...] Luckily, he can rely on the know-how of his political-veteran deputy Arpi [...] and the dedication of his offbeat staff to keep him on the right path, as well as some inspiration from his teenage daughter [Orly Bremer].

When I learned that Fey co-created *Mr. Mayor*, I immediately suspected that there would be at least one self-sexualized teen in the series, but I was wrong, because Orly was sexualized. And that theme was apparent in the trailer where, unsurprisingly, Orly's teen sexuality was used to promote the streaming series. For example, in the trailer, Jaden assumed that Orly, whom was played by 17-year-old Kyla Kenedy, was Mayor Bremer's wife. After Orly and Mayor Bremer, who was played by 74-year-old Ted Danson, protested, Jaden implied that age-gap marriages were common in L.A.. That scene, which aired on the co-written by Fey pilot, was centered around Mayor Bremer's straw ban that was enacted to reduce waste from local businesses and to prevent harm to turtles.

Orly, "You have to cancel this stupid straw ban!"

Jaden, "Your wife makes a great point."

Mayor Bremer, "She's my teenage daughter, [Jaden] Kwapis!"

Orly, "Ew!"

Jaden, "I'm so sorry. It's very confusing in L.A."

Also on the trailer, Tommy Tomás, the Mayor's Chief Strategist, commended Mayor Bremer for raising Orly well. Specifically, because Orly was not a (teen) stripper.

Chief Strategist Tommy, "You raised Orly right, sir. No stripping for her."

Mayor Bremer, "What?"

Interestingly, those lines were in the trailer, but I don't recall hearing them in any episodes. Am I mistaken or were they in the trailer as streambait?

In addition, Orly was shown in the trailer in her private schoolgirl uniform with her plaid pleated skirt barely reaching mid-thigh. Unlike the boarding schoolgirls in Scarlett Thomas' *Oligarchy* and the Manhattan schoolgirls in Andrew Trees' *Academy X*, I would imagine that Orly did not voluntarily roll up her skirt, but I suspect that someone in the costume department gave it to her at that leering length. (However, Orly's skirt was not as high as Karen's, which, as you may recall, barely covered her "perky" heinie.)

And throughout the *Mr. Mayor* episodes, Orly appeared inexplicably at City Hall in her schoolgirl uniform. For example, on "Brentwood Trash" (season 01 episode 03), a pipe burst at Orly's school, which inexplicably shut down the entire private school. Consequently, instead of going

home, Orly wore her shortened schoolgirl uniform to City Hall. Orly, "Is my dad around? A pipe burst at school; so, they let us go early." Subsequently, during the same scene, Orly shared with Mikaela Shaw, the mayor's chief of staff and an influencer, "I can't believe her! Whatever." Intriguingly, Mikaela assumed that Orly was distraught because, à la Swiffer Girl and Karen, Orly's teen nudes had been leaked. Mikaela, "What's wrong? Leaked nudes. [By a] Frenemy?" But it turned out that Orly was upset because she was initially given "first chair" in the school's orchestra concert, "[...] but then Mr. Kenny gave the solo in "Peer Gynt" to Abby Shapiro [...]"

Later in the season on "I'm rich, and this is L.A." (season 1 episode 8), I was reminded that Jaden was correct to assume that Orly was married to Mayor Bremer, because on the episode which was, of course, co-written by Fey, in reference to his latest love interest, Mayor Bremer said, "Nicole is a very nice age-appropriate lady." However, Deputy Mayor Arpi Meskimen replied, "She's young enough to be your daughter," to which Mayor Bremer replied, "I'm rich, and this is L.A.."

And lastly, in terms of Fey's portrayal of age-gap relationships, back in the pilot episode, Mikaela shared that by getting the job as the mayor's chief of staff, she could, "[...] finally break up with that gross doctor." #sugardaddy

In closing, due to other writing projects, time didn't permit me to study Fey's other creations like the 139 episodes of her *30 Rock*; however, it may be clear from *Unbreakable Kimmy Schmidt*, *Mean Girls*, and *Mr. Mayor* that Fey has used the allure of (self) sexualized teens to sell Broadway tickets and streaming subscriptions. Of course, Fey is not alone in this regard. Other female creators and writers have used the allure of nymphets to get streams. For example, Mindy Kaling co-created the Netflix series *Never Have I Ever* (2020) where 15-year-old Devi prayed for "a stone-cold hottie who can rock me all night long" After Devi's classmate asked about the size of their schoolmate's penis, "Is his penis as big as it looks in those sweatpants?", Devi shared, "It's like I think about sex 24-7." And on HBO Max's *The Sex Lives of College Girls*, which was co-created by Kaling, 18-year-old Bela professed in the premiere that she desired to have sex with (48-year-old) television host Seth Meyers, and Bela exclaimed to her roommates, "I [just] gave six handjob!"

DIALOGUE/ LYRIC	SUGGESTION [For a High School Student]
"Take your top off!"	Option not to say that line.
"And then in the spring, we do Condoms and Choking."	"And then in the spring, we do Self-esteem and Choking."
"And if you like blowing...and fingering."	And if you like marching with tromboners.
"Hahaha! That is tits!--" "She means, that's great!"	Option not to say that line.
Well, who are you?! We haven't had new meat in our little lady taco in so long.	Well, who is this new badass Girlboss Power Beyotch?!
"Karen's had sex with eleven people and I've never told anyone." "That's good of you."	"Karen's hooked up with eleven people and I've never told anyone." "That's good of you."
"Thank you, that would be tits!"	"Thank you, that would be awesome!"
"Karen, I can see your bra." "It's on purpose. I'm going for a look." "Is it a girl who slept with eleven people? 'Cause you're nailing it."	"Karen, I can see your bra." "It's on purpose. I'm going for a look." "If it's 'girl who hooked up with eleven people' you're nailing it."
"Awwwwwww...Don't bring me no little-ass white girl booty!"	"Awwwwwww...Don't bring me no little butt rich girl booty!"
"What does this say? Caitlyn Caussin has what? "Hairy nips."	"What does this say? Caitlyn Caussin has what? "Chin hairs."

Libretto Vocal Book *Mean Girls: High School Version* (Revised July 2022):

Approved changes from the unedited Broadway version